

Deliverable 1.2 - Final version of the Community webpage containing all outcomes

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the creation, publication, and final update of the Community webpage that brings together all project outcomes. The page was revised from an initially project-centric format to one that clearly reflects the Community's long-term purpose, role, and mode of operation beyond the project lifetime. The updated content clearly communicates the benefits of participating in the Community and highlights key Community outputs to demonstrate the value generated for members and for the wider scientific and Research Data Management (RDM) community at large.

Document info

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Dissemination level <i>(PU/ RE/CO)</i>	PU

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

RDM	Research Data Management

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Final version of the Community webpage containing all outcomes

This deliverable covers the creation, publication, and final update of the Community webpage¹ consolidating all project outcomes. The initial version of the page was more white-paper and project-focused, while the revised version, currently only available as a preview for internal use, better reflects the Community's long-term purpose, scope, and goals beyond the project lifetime. The content was reshaped to clearly communicate the benefits of participating in the Community, helping potential new members understand its value and role. In addition, a dedicated section highlighting key Community outputs was added to showcase the tangible value generated for members and for the wider scientific and Research Data Management (RDM) community at large. The new content will be made available on the Community webpage shortly after the completion of this deliverable.

Outcomes and expected impact

The updated webpage provides a sustainable and accessible entry point to the Community, strengthening visibility and engagement. By shifting focus from project reporting to long-lasting Community goals and outputs, the page supports onboarding of new members and reinforces the Community's role within ELIXIR. The clear presentation of key outputs demonstrates the Community's impact, promotes reuse of its resources, and supports data stewards, researchers, and RDM professionals beyond the project context.

Dissemination Plans

The RDM Community webpage is available at the ELIXIR Europe website².

This report will be uploaded to Zenodo within the ELIXIR Zenodo Community³.

¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/research-data-management>

² <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/research-data-management>

³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/elixir>